

A STUDY ON THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF BORDEURI GAON, LAKHIMPUR DISTRICT, ASSAM

Simi Barman

M.A, M.Ed.

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Abstract

In this research paper, the investigator tries to find out the socio-economic condition of Bordeuri gaon. The researcher's main focus was to observe the socio-economic condition of the village. So, the investigator selected the whole village as the research population and selected 19 villagers as a sample. A descriptive survey method is used in this research. Data are collected through open-ended and close-ended questionnaires and unstructured interviews. Collected data are analyzed through statistical tools. The researcher tries to explore the actual living standard of the people of Bordeuri gaon.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Bordeuri village is located in Narayanpur subdivision of Lakhimpur district in Assam, India. It is 4 km from the sub-district headquarters Narayanpur, and 50 km from district headquarters, North Lakhimpur. The total geographical area of the village is 368.69 hectares. Bordeuri has a total population of 2659, out of which the male population is 1316 while the female population is 1343. The literacy rate of Bordeuri village is 69.20%, out of which female literacy rate is 30.5%. Bordeuri village gaon panchayat name is Pub Narayanpur. It is imperative in a society to maintain the minimum standard of living, eradicate traditional thinking, support scientific and modern concepts in every aspect of society, and so on. The villagers face various socio-economic problems like lack of proper education, sanitation, pure and safe drinking water, electrification, etc. Different geographical and economic characteristics of a region can be observed and analyzed at the micro level. The socio-economic condition of an area plays a significant role in studying the region's development. So it is imperative to research rural areas so the village can develop in every aspect.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

The main objective of this survey study is about the Bordeori villager's environment and socio-economic status of Bordeori village.

- (1) To study about the physiography of Bordeori gaon. The climate transportation flora and fauna, soil type, drainage and demography of the region.
- (2) To study about the socio-economic status of the region.
- (3) To study the standard of living of the area's people.
- (4) To study to access the availability of rural services in the area (drinking water, health, education and other infrastructure facilities, etc)
- (5) To examine the accessibility and transport and communication facilities in the area.

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The village is located in the Narayanpur region, Lakhimpur district. The researcher studied the village's unique and attractive condition and analyzed its socio-economic characteristics. The purpose of this survey is to help the district administration draw an action plan for the district's socio-economic and infrastructure development to improve the quality of life of the people and reduce the economic balance.

4. METHODOLOGY:

A descriptive survey method was used. A direct open-ended interview was conducted through a questionnaire, and opinions were solicited from the Bordeori gaon household. Ask them many questions to get information about their socio-economic status. The researcher has prepared a survey schedule to study the local people's socio-economic status.

5. PHYSICAL SETTING OF THE STUDY AREA:

The village is situated in the north Lakhimpur district of Assam. North Lakhimpur district is situated in the northeast part of Assam. Narayanpur is a vast area situated in the Middle Eastern part of the district. And bordeori gaon is located on the east side of this vast Narayanpur region. The Lakhimpur district of Assam is between 26.48.00" and 27.53.00 north latitude and 93.42.00 east longitude. The village is situated between these coordinate extensions.

Climate and rainfall:

In Bordeori gaon the climate is warm and temperate. There is a great deal of rainfall in Bordeori gaon. Even in the driest month. The kopper- geiger climate classification is Cfa. The average annual temperature is 23.9 c in bordeori gaon—precipitation here averages 2945 mm.

Soil

In this village, two types of soil are found. New alluvial soil (1) New alluvial soil: The new alluvial soils are found in the floodplain area, are subjected to occasional floods, and consequently receive considerable silt deposits after the flood recedes. These are yellow to yellowish-grey in colour and are admixtures of sand, silt and clay in varying proportions. Mineral weathering and geo-chemical change are nominal. However, incipient changes in the top layer have been noticed due to biological activity. Soil P.H. is feebly alkaline and moderately rich in plant nutrients.

Flora and fauna

Some trees are found in this village, like Mango, Shal, Jack fruit, Papaya, and Guava tree. Crow, Cuckoo, Dove etc birds are found in this village. Many orchids are also found in this village.

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Family size

Before studying in any area, the study of the size of housing and families is most important. There is a great impact on income and standard of living by the size. Many families have 5,6 members. Family size is also an important aspect of the region's demographic structure, which is measured by dividing the total population by the total household. The researcher randomly selected five households for my study, and I have a total population of 19.

Age structure

Fig: 1 Age structure

The population of an area can be studied more specifically with the age structure of Bordeori gaon is shown in figure 1, which is a part of Narayanpur region. With the surveyed data, we get the age structure of Bordeori gaon. The figure shows that the number of people between

the age groups 15 and 60 is highest in that village and the group above 60 has the lowest population.

Sex ratio

Fig2: sex ratio

Sex ratio means the number of females per 1000 males found in an area. Figure no2 shows the male population dominates this village, but there is no more difference with the female population.

Religion

This village is dominated by the Hindu population.

Ethnic group

Ethnic group means different racial or cultural groups of people. Only one ethnic group is found in this region. As per the figure, we identified that only Deori people dominated that whole region.

Education qualification:

Fig3: Education qualifications

In this village, only five households were considered for the study. Literacy is an educational factor of the human index, and when the researcher took five households randomly, then the result was quite different. I have found that 20% of the illiterate, 40% of L.P. pass, 6.66% of M.E pass, 20.% of H.S. pass, and only 13.33% of other vocational education. So here we are sure that L.P. passes are the maximum in this village and there are no college pass people.

Occupation structure

Fig4: Occupation structure

The occupation pattern of an area or a state depends on the availability of natural resources or technological development, which influences the livelihood pattern of the society or community. Moreover, occupation controls the socio-economic condition of the people. Bordeori gaon is a village situated in a plain area. It is located in the Brahmaputra valley. Most of the people of Bordeori gaon are involved in cultivation; the researcher observed that people engage in poultry, weaving, and other activities. Poor education and lack of skilled labour are the main reasons for such poor economic status.

Total land per family

Fig5: total land

To check the actual socio economic status of a region, it is also a important to study about the total land per household. The figure shows that maximum people have land 5 pura to 10 pura, and so the main occupation of this region is cultivation.

Total rice production:

Fig 6: Total rice productions

This diagram shows that maximum household's production are sufficient for the year. This diagram easily indicate one thing that this village's economic condition will not be so rich or so poor, because their production are sufficient for the year but not for sale or not only for 3 or 6 months.

Prayer attending:

Fig7: prayer attending

From this figure, it is clear that every household attends prayer differently. 20% of people attend daily, 20% participate in weekly, 20% attend elsewhere, and 40% attend not at all. So it is clear from this study that every household is a little concerned about prayer but not so religious, too, because the researcher did not get the result that 100% attend prayer daily.

Participate in function:

Fig 8: taking part in the function

Figure shows that the percentage of no response is more than yes. So, it is confirmed that people are more involved in cultural activities.

Reading newspaper/magazine:

Fig9: Reading newspaper/magazine

The figure also shows that no response is more than yes. So, it is clear that the people of this village are no longer involved with any educational purpose. Most of them do not have the facility to buy any newspaper or magazine. There is no bookstall in their village.

Heath status

Sources of drinking water:

Figure 10: Sources of drinking water:

Wells are the main source of drinking water in this village. The diagram shows that the well is the source of drinking water for 40% of people in the village, 20% of people depend on tube wells as a source of their drinking water, and 20% of people's drinking water source is motor.

Diseases depend on

Fig11: Diseases depend on

Figures show that all people depend on doctors. By asking them, the researcher can know that, in some situations, they also rely on rituals, but they always give first preference to the doctor.

Health visitors visit

Fig12: health visitors visit

The diagram shows that doctors often come to this village to check the health of the villagers. 40% of people responded that they often get this facility to check their health freely through health visitors. However, the other 60% of people responded that they do not get any of these types of free health check-ups.

Types of Sanitation

Fig13: Type of Sanitation

40% of people responded that they use the Pucca latrine. It was a good result that they used pure sanitary latrines, and 60% of people answered that they used pit-type latrines. Studying the sanitation system is more important than studying the socio-economic status of a region.

Using electricity/balanced diet / visiting school to meet the teacher

These three questions we have put on the questionnaire. However, all these responses were 100% No or Yes, according to the question. All reactions were yes to using electricity, and there was no balanced diet, and none of them ever visited any school to meet a teacher.

Some general information about the village

1. Distance from the town= 2k.m from Narayanpur
2. Main community = Deori
3. Total families =435
4. General occupation= Cultivation
5. Total numbers of schools=

L.P school	1
M.E School	4
High school	3
College	1
Namghar	1
Hospital	0
Co-operative store	5
Non formal educational centre	2

6. Any social evil = No

7. FINDINGS:

Bordeori gaon is a village of Narayanpur region with very natural beauty. Science and technology have come to be recognized as major to all progress. The economy of this village is rural economy. The Madhabdev College and the schools are great assets of this region.

Here are some key factors that would affect the socio-economic status of the village-

- (1) The economy is mostly affected during the rainy season as there is the problem of mud. During rainy days, mud makes the movement of people and great very difficult.
- (2) The people practice traditional methods of cultivation due to the lack of modern tools.
- (3) Most of the people in the rural areas are deprived of any government aid and facilities like water supply, medical facilities, education, housing, etc., which affects the lives of the people in the study area.
- (4) The transport facilities are also not so good. Markets are far away from the village, and there are no public bus services.
- (5) Due to the parents' lack of consciousness, their children are not as educated. For this reason, in almost all rural areas, the literacy rate is relatively low, and the number of youths with a higher level of education is minimal.

8. SUGGESTIONS:

For the socio-economic development of this region, the primary strategy is to improve the standard of living of the people in this area. Infrastructure facilities and government facilities, such as little financial support, water supply, medical facilities, and educational and transportation facilities, should be made available to all the people. There is no market in this village, just some small shops are found near the school area. Farmers should be encouraged to use modern agricultural equipment and techniques, such as fertilizers and pesticides.

9. CONCLUSION:

This report clearly shows that the village is yet to be modernized. The region is poor in medical facilities. A minimum of them have pigs but don't know how to keep them. The natural beauty and its favourable climate act as an advantage for the inhabitants. Some are engaged in small shops. If they use modern technology, they will be able to share a very developing village in that region. It is quite clear that the village is still backward. The government has to emphasize the development of agriculture. Better medical facilities, educational Institutes, transport and communication, better marketing facilities, and good schemes for poultry horticulture are some of the major aspects that need to be developed urgently. Especially health and medical facilities are some of the major aspects that need to be developed urgently. Thus, this study plays an enormous role in inspiring our knowledge, experience, and information about the people of remote areas. This region can develop faster if it gets government support for modern technology, social awareness, and transport facilities. In this research, the researcher studied the problems of the region where the people are mainly dependent on cultivation, and there are no other types of such income sources. The government has to emphasize the development of agriculture. Apart from that, better medical facilities, educational institutions, marketing facilities, better reading conditions, and transportation facilities are some of the significant requirements that need to be developed in this region.

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